

MARINE PLACER OCCURRENCES AND ASSOCIATED CRITICAL RAW MATERIALS IN RIAS BAIXAS (NW SPAIN)

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Abstract

Rias Baixas, a funnel-shaped estuarine inflow system into the coastal drainage area located in NW Spain, is mainly surrounded by Variscan metamorphic and intrusive coastal outcrops. Heavy mineral placer occurrences and deposits were formed in coastal areas by weathering of these rocks. Balarés beach (Ponteceso, Coruña) is an example, 3,600 tonnes of ilmenite (Ti) and other by-products (garnet, zircon, rutile, monazite and cassiterite) were extracted from this deposit between 1941 and 1952. This work is part of the European HORIZON project S34i (<https://s34i.eu/>) and summarizes the first results to evaluate the critical raw materials (CRM) associated with placers in the coastal areas of the Ría de Vigo. Baluarte and Fontaiña (Vao Beach), Límens, Santa Marta, Alemans, Ratas and Canabal beaches were explored in March and September 2023, while potential placer occurrences were recognized according to IGME internal reports (1976 and 1979). Ten sandy-sediment samples were collected in the heavy minerals-enriched surface layer in March 2023. At each site, three different sampling points were taken from 1 cm depth within an area of 1 m². Organic matter and carbonate were eliminated, and then the samples were graded by granulometry. Fine to medium sands (<0.250 - >0.125 mm) were selected for heavy mineral separation by liquid density using bromoform. Geochemical analysis was carried out using ICP-MS. In the field trips were identified two main placer occurrences: Santa Marta and Vao Beach. Both areas are dominated by reddish accumulations of heavy minerals in multilayers to a depth of about 50 cm. Surface patches of black minerals (about 1 to 10 m²) characterise the other beaches and the western part of Santa Marta Beach. Granulometry shows medium to fine sands, and heavy mineral contents have been quantified up to 46%, in multilayer enriched. In addition, Vao and Santa Marta samples show high accumulation of Zr, Nb, Hf, Ta, Th, U, La, Ce, Nd, Sm and others (bulk sample). Further analysis is underway to quantify the percentage weight of each heavy mineral. The placer occurrences in the Rias Baixas show great potential for CRM accumulation, especially close to the sand and crystalline rock substrate contact at the beaches, and in depositional centres in shallow waters areas.

Keyword

Placers, CRM, heavy mineral, sand